

HOT AND SINTER FORGING OF ZIRCONIA DISPERSED ALUMINA PRODUCED BY REACTION BONDING

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ABSTRACT

The superplastic-like deformation behavior of reaction bonded, zirconia dispersed alumina has been investigated in compression at 1350 - 1500°C under stresses of 10 - 200 MPa. The stress exponent equals 1.4 at low temperature and increases to 1.7 at high temperature. The apparent activation energy increases from 629 kJ/mol at low stress to 736 kJ/mol at high stress. Grain boundary sliding is the dominant deformation mechanism. Possible rate limiting steps are discussed.

Densification and plastic forming are combined into one step during sinter forging. A reduction of the sintering temperature by 200°C compared to free sintering has been realized. The sinter forging kinetics are analyzed by means of interrupted tests at 1320°C under initial stresses of 20 - 45 MPa.

INTRODUCTION

Reaction bonding of Al₂O₃ (RBAO) has been developed recently at TUHH [1] as an alternative to conventional processing of alumina ceramics. In this process, nanosized RBAO precursor powders are produced by attrition milling of Al/Al₂O₃ powder mixtures. During heat treatment in air at temperatures below 1000°C, the metal phase in RBAO compacts fully converts to nanometer sized oxide crystallites which bond the primary Al₂O₃ particles. The volume expansion (28%) associated with the Al→Al₂O₃ transition partially compensates for the shrinkage occurring during sintering at temperatures near 1500°C. Incorporation of other metal or ceramic phases, exhibiting larger volume expansion upon oxidation, can be used to further compensate for the sintering shrinkage. In addition to its low-to-zero shrinkage capability, other attributes of the RBAO-process like low raw material costs, suitability for incorporating non-equiaxed second phases (platelets, fibers) and excellent green state machinability make this technique very attractive for high-performance applications.

In the present investigation, the reaction bonding technology has been used to prepare zirconia dispersed alumina composites (20 vol% ZrO₂). The incorporation of zirconia particles is an essential prerequisite to obtain a fine microstructure. The dispersion of fine zirconia particles effectively suppresses both static and dynamic grain growth of alumina by a pinning mechanism [2]. Recently, we have demonstrated [3] that superplastic forming in biaxial tension of this material is possible at a temperature of 1500 °C or more. Uniaxial compression tests have been

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used to determine the dominant deformation mechanism and the latest results will be given here. The creep characteristics have been interpreted in terms of the phenomenological flow law:

$$\dot{\epsilon} = A \exp\left(-\frac{Q}{RT}\right) \frac{\sigma^n}{d^p} \quad (1)$$

where $\dot{\epsilon}$ is the observed strain rate in the z (compression) direction, A is a numerical constant, Q the apparent activation energy, σ the applied stress, n the stress exponent, d the grain size, p the grain size exponent and RT has its usual meaning.

Densification and forming are combined into one process step during sinter forging. Here, a porous body is subjected to a uniaxial compressive stress without lateral constraint. In this way, large creep strains can be imposed on the sintering material, which leads to an elimination of processing flaws and hence to a improvement of mechanical properties. Results of sinter forging tests of RBAO will be given below. Creep and densification have been separated by means of interrupted tests.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

POWDER SYNTHESIS AND REACTION BONDING

A powder mixture, having a composition (codename K20) of 45 vol% Al (Alcan 105, 5-50 μm , Alcan International, Canada), 35 vol% Al_2O_3 (Ceralox MPA-4, Condea Chemie, FRG) and 20 vol% 2 mol% yttria stabilized tetragonal zirconia (TZ-2Y, Tosoh Co., Japan), was attrition milled in acetone using zirconia milling balls for 7 h at 700 rpm. These milling conditions were previously determined to be the optimum ones for effective comminution of the Al particles and successful fabrication of dense, fully oxidized RBAO [4,5]. After rotovap and air drying of the powders, green compacts were made by uniaxial compaction under 50 MPa and isostatic compaction under 300 MPa.

Reaction bonding was carried out in two steps: a first heating cycle for oxidation and a second one for densification. In the first cycle green bodies are slowly ($1^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$) heated in air to 1100°C . Between 300 and 900°C the Al completely oxidizes to $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$, which transforms to $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ upon further heating. In the second cycle the oxidized body is heated at $5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ to 1550°C , followed by a 1 h dwell, to obtain a dense (95% or more) material. More details concerning powder processing and reaction bonding mechanisms can be found elsewhere [5].

Specimens used for hot forging experienced the full reaction bonding cycle, whereas specimens used for sinter forging were only subjected to the oxidation cycle. Coarser grained samples for hot forging were made by annealing at 1650°C for 3 - 20 hours. These samples had to be post-HIPed (1550°C , 180 MPa, 20 min, in Ar) after annealing, to obtain a density of 95% prior to deformation. The residual porosity was concentrated in the core of these HIPed samples.

HIGH TEMPERATURE DEFORMATION

Rectangular samples for hot and sinter forging tests were sawn from sintered bars and machined to their final dimensions (5 mm x 3 mm x 3 mm). Hot forging tests were performed in air using a screw-driven universal testing machine (Zwick 1478, FRG). Axial displacement was measured externally during all tests. Specimens were heated at $7^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ to $1000^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, followed by heating at $15^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ to the test temperature. After temperature equilibration, samples were

compressed under constant stress to a true strain of 0.5, after which they were rapidly cooled down under load. True strains of 1.0 could be achieved, but to avoid non-uniaxial and friction conditions the maximum allowed strain was set at 0.5. Tests were performed at 1350 - 1500°C under stresses of 10 - 200 MPa. Creep curves were recorded for various stresses at 1450°C by compression to 0.5 under a single stress value. At all other temperatures, stress stepping experiments have been performed; the stress being raised after a true strain increment of ~0.1.

Sinter forging tests were performed in air at 1320°C using a home-made dead-weight loading machine. Displacement was measured internally by means of a LVDT, located centrally below the upper loading ram. Therefore, specimens had to be placed slightly away from the center of the loading train, which led to some shearing at higher stresses and strains, as will be discussed further below. Specimens were heated at 8°C/min to 1000°C/min, followed by heating at 15°C/min to 1320°C. Compression took place under constant loads, corresponding to initial stresses of 20, 30 and 45 MPa. At different stages of deformation tests were interrupted by quickly removing the load, followed by cooling down at 15°C/min. For every test, a new specimen has been used. Creep and densification have been separated using the method proposed by Raj [6]. The plastic strain in the compression (z) direction (ϵ_c), hereafter referred to as creep strain, is given by:

$$\epsilon_c = \left| \epsilon_z - (\epsilon_v / 3) \right| \quad (2)$$

where ϵ_z is the axial strain and ϵ_v is the volumetric strain.

CHARACTERIZATION METHODS

Densities of samples with closed porosity were determined by the Archimedes method (in water), whereas for samples with open porosity densities were determined geometrically. Microstructures in the as-sintered state were examined by electron microscopy. Grain sizes were determined by the linear intercept technique from both SEM micrographs of polished, thermally etched cuts or TEM micrographs of thin sections. TEM foils (3 mm diameter) were made by diamond sawing, followed by grinding, ultrasound drilling and polishing down to 50 μm thickness. Thinning to electron transparency took place by dimple grinding and ion milling. The foils were coated with a thin carbon layer to prevent charging in the electron microscope.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

UNIAXIAL COMPRESSION

Creep curves of dense (95 - 97%) RBAO with a mean alumina grain size of 0.94 μm were obtained at 1450°C under stresses of 10 to 200 MPa. After a primary creep regime of 1 - 2%, steady-state is reached for all stresses except the lowest one for which very minor strain hardening is observed. This virtual absence of strain hardening demonstrates that the dispersion of fine zirconia particles effectively suppresses the strong strain-enhanced grain growth observed for pure Al_2O_3 under dynamic conditions. The absence of dynamic grain growth is corroborated by TEM observations. The microstructure remains equiaxed after deformation [3].

Fig.1 shows the observed strain rate as a function of stress at 1350 - 1500°C in a double-logarithmic plot. The stress required to obtain a strain rate of $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$, suitable for superplastic forming, increases from 18 MPa at 1500°C to 100 MPa at 1400°C. The stress exponent n , calculated from the slope of the curves of Fig.1 decreases with temperature: at 1450 - 1500°C n

Figure 1. Stress-dependence of strain rate during compression at 1350 - 1500°C

Figure 2. The apparent activation energy as a function of stress

Figure 3. Strain rate versus grain size during compression at 1450°C under various stresses

equals 1.7, while at 1350 - 1400°C n has decreased to 1.4. These values agree well with the average value determined for n from the individual stress jumps of the stress stepping experiments. Fig.2 shows the apparent activation energy, as determined from Arrhenius-plots of the strain rates of Fig.1, as a function of stress. A clear increase of the activation energy with stress is observed: Q increases from 629 ± 16 kJ/mol at 30 MPa to 736 ± 92 kJ/mol at 200 MPa.

The grain size dependence of strain rate at 1450°C under various stresses can be seen in Fig.3 for grain sizes from 1 to 3 μm . The limited data seem to suggest that the grain size dependence becomes stronger with increasing grain size at this temperature, independent of the applied stress. The grain size exponent p equals approximately 2.5 above 2 μm , whereas p is close to 1 below 2 μm . At 1350°C such a transition is not observed and p equals approximately 1. In general, the stress exponent decreases slightly and the ductility decreases strongly with increasing grain size.

SINTER FORGING

An initial set of sinter forging tests under stresses of 45 - 60 MPa showed that the minimum temperature required to obtain >95% dense RBAO by this pressure assisted sintering technique equals 1300°C. Dilatometer experiments demonstrated that similar densities can only be reached at 1500°C or more by pressureless sintering. The application of a uniaxial load thus permits a reduction of the sintering temperature by 200°C in the case of RBAO.

A more detailed analysis of the sinter forging kinetics has therefore been performed at 1320°C by means of interrupted tests. Fig.4 shows the increase of density with time during free sintering and sinter forging under initial stresses of 20, 30 and 45 MPa. Clearly, the sinterability increases drastically with stress. Whereas the free sintering sample shows hardly any increase in density, 95% density is reached after 3 hours during sinter forging under 45 MPa. Raising the temperature to 1350°C reduces the sintering time further to only 30 min under this stress.

During sinter forging the sample may contract or expand in the radial direction, depending on the relative magnitude of sintering and creep. Sinter forging is the only sintering technique, where the processing path is not fixed and can be tuned by the applied stress. It thus truly combines forming and densification, albeit limited to simple shapes. Fig.5 shows the processing path, radial versus axial strain, of the present experiments. From this diagram it is clear that under all stresses the samples expand radially, the expansion increasing with stress. Furthermore, it is interesting to note that before reaching full density, the processing paths become parallel to the isodensity-contours. This transition to virtually pure creep occurs at a density of ~94%.

The second way to represent the processing path is shown in Fig.6, where the volumetric strain is plotted versus creep strain. It can be seen that at a particular volumetric strain, i.e. at a particular density, the amount of plastic strain experienced by the sinter forging material increases with stress. Upon reaching their end density (95%) large creep strains have been imposed on the specimens; e.g. 0.6 under 30 MPa and 0.9 under 45 MPa.

The stress dependence of creep rate has also been analyzed at different densities. The stress exponent (n) equals 2.5 at 70% density and increases to 4.1 at 90% density. Careful inspection of the data and the macroscopic appearance of the forged samples show, however, that this strong increase of n can only be explained by shearing of the samples. The amount of shearing increases with increasing stress and strain, which leads to anomalously high stress exponents at densities above 70%.

Figure 4. Increase of density with time during free sintering (0 MPa) and sinter forging at 1320°C under 20 - 45 MPa.

Figure 5. The processing path radial versus axial strain of the present experiments

Figure 6. The processing path volumetric versus creep strain of the present experiments

DISCUSSION

The uniaxial compression tests have shown that superplastic flow of RBAO containing 20 vol% 2Y-TZP is characterized by a stress exponent of 1.7 at high temperature (1450 - 1500°C) and 1.4 at lower temperatures (1350 - 1400°C). Both for fine-grained MgO-doped alumina [7] and Y-TZP [8] single phase materials, it has been demonstrated that the creep rates are controlled by diffusional and interface reaction controlled grain boundary sliding acting in series. The creep rate has a σ/d^3 -dependence for the first mechanism and a σ^2/d -dependence for the latter. Small grain size, low stress and low temperature favor interface reaction control. Curve fitting of the data of Fig. 1, however, showed that this description does not hold for the present experiments. The best fit was rather obtained by a function of 2 parallel processes; one having a linear and the other having a cube stress-dependence. The contribution of the latter mechanism becomes larger with higher temperature.

A transition from $n=1$ to $n=3$ with an increase of stress has been well documented from bending tests of coarser grained alumina. Both dislocation activity and cavitation flow have been put forward to explain the high stress behavior. Dörre & Hübner [9] discarded dislocation creep, because the von Mises criterium of 5 independent slip systems is never fulfilled as a consequence of the very high critical shear stress of the pyramidal slip system. Nevertheless, some basal texture has been observed for the alumina phase in the RBAO samples compressed at 1450°C in this investigation. Such a basal texture was absent prior to deformation. Cavitation flow might be the appropriate explanation for the high stress-regime during bending of alumina, because of the relatively easy grain boundary separation of this material under tensile loading. For the present investigation this does not seem to hold, because the material is deformed in compression and the grain boundary cohesion of ZrO₂-dispersed alumina is much higher than that of pure alumina. Furthermore, following the argument of cavitation flow, one would expect the coarser grained RBAO samples to exhibit higher stress exponents than the fine-grained ones, which is not the case.

The apparent activation energy for creep, determined here, increased from 629 kJ/mol at 30 MPa to 736 kJ/mol at 200 MPa. A similar increase of Q with stress was reported by Wakai [10]: 633 kJ/mol at 10 MPa to 753 kJ/mol at 50 MPa. These activation energies are in the same range as those determined for boundary diffusion-controlled sintering (700 kJ/mol) [11] and grain growth [2] (732 kJ/mol) of ZrO₂-added alumina. These boundary diffusion activation energies are quite high compared to that of Al₂O₃ (420 - 440 kJ/mol [7]). This increase in activation energy in transition metal oxide doped alumina has been attributed to an increase of the enthalpy for defect formation [12] or an increase in the grain boundary cohesion [11]. However, the activation energies determined here are influenced by the change of stress exponent with temperature. By curve fitting one can eliminate this effect. An Arrhenius diagram of the curve fitting constants gave $Q=486$ kJ/mol for the $n=1$ mechanism and $Q=919$ kJ/mol for the $n=3$ mechanism. The first value is in very good agreement with the boundary diffusion activation energy for pure alumina mentioned above.

A drastic enhancement of the sinterability of RBAO was observed here by applying a uniaxial stress during sintering. The sintering temperature could be lowered by 200°C. He *et al.* [13] demonstrated that they could lower the sintering temperature of wet chemically prepared ZrO₂-dispersed alumina with 100°C by sinter forging, while Boutz *et al.* [14] reported a reduction of 50°C in the case of wet chemically prepared Y,Ce-TZP. The larger reduction of composite materials compared to the monolithic one is probably related to stresses that develop during sintering of the composite material, due to the difference in sintering rate of both constituents. These stresses retard sintering, but can relax by creep of the matrix during sinter forging. Furthermore, He *et al.* also demonstrated that the difference in sintering kinetics of ZTA-powders calcined at different temperatures are much smaller during sinter forging than during free sintering. The larger benefit of sinter forging is thus observed for the worse sintering

material. This can be understood by the fact that the pore size distribution becomes more homogeneous by creep of the material during sinter forging as compared to free sintering [15]

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The deformation behaviour of reaction bonded, zirconia dispersed alumina is Newtonian ($n=1$) at low temperature, but becomes non-Newtonian at higher temperature, due to the contribution of a mechanism having a cube stress dependence. Grain boundary diffusion controlled grain boundary sliding with dislocation creep contributing at higher temperature are the most plausible mechanisms. Dislocation activity during high temperature deformation of RBAO will be studied in more depth in the near future. The potential of sinter forging to produce fine-grained, high strength parts will be a second focus of future research.

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